

Ways to Effectively Use Marketing Tools To Increase The Export of Fruit and Vegetable Products

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Abstract:

The article provides regular supply of processing enterprises with raw materials, stable saturation of the domestic consumer market with vegetables, potatoes, fruits and melons, increasing the volume of export of wet and processed fruits and vegetables, demanded and competitive in foreign markets. and the establishment of a unified procurement system and the development of fruit and vegetable products in the country along with the importance of exports for the country's economy. Scientifically grounded proposals and recommendations on promising opportunities to further increase exports among producers are developed.

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Introduction

Today, Uzbekistan has become an independent state in the international community and has become a member of influential international organizations. It has established political, diplomatic, trade-economic and cultural ties with leading industrialized countries in the world, and has been developing bilateral and multilateral mutually beneficial ties. In these circumstances, the country's foreign economic potential is the availability of natural resources, the creation of industrial and scientific and technical potential, the export of infrastructure, social services, products and services abroad or to foreign nationals, firms, organizations, including foreign businesses and joint ventures. sales to businesses.

The most important economic indicators that determine the country's foreign economic potential are the volume of GDP production, including the per capita GDP, the share of exports of goods and services and the share of industrial goods in the total volume of exports.

As we know, one of the traditional and most advanced forms of international economic relations is foreign trade. Foreign trade accounts for 75-80% of the total volume of international economic relations taking place in the world economy. Foreign trade is important for any country in the world.

According to the Decree "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "development of new types of products and technologies in principle, ensuring competitiveness of national goods in domestic and foreign markets [1] is important." - Stable supply of foodstuffs at the expense of domestic opportunities, as well as increase in export of agricultural products bee is given special attention.

In this regard, the present study provides for the provision of domestic processing enterprises with raw materials, stable saturation of the domestic consumer market with fruits and vegetables throughout the year, as well as increasing the export of wet and processed fruits and vegetables, which are in demand and competitive in foreign markets. and extending the scope of their cultivation, production and procurement to expand their range.

At the same time, scientifically sound proposals and recommendations will be developed to regulate the export of fruit and vegetable products, to improve the existing mechanism of insurance of export contracts, as well as to implement marketing research methods to increase exports of these products.

The prospects of introduction of modern high-tech equipment for the processing of fruit and vegetables by leading foreign manufacturers will be discussed.

The positive impact on the development of the sector is exempted from customs duties on the import of modern equipment and technologies, regardless of their affiliation, in the form of private property processing of fruit and vegetable products.

The main areas of activities, which are intended to be used for technical re-equipment and modernization of production, will be highlighted by means of tax and customs benefits provided to enterprises.

Literature review

Adam Smith, the founder of the economic sciences, strongly criticizes mercantilism. He and his followers argue that free trade is important and beneficial to all international trade participants, but that the state's active involvement in economic processes is detrimental to the country's economy [2].

According to economist J. Saks, "the economic success of any country in the world is reflected in foreign trade. So far, no country has been able to create a healthy economy isolated from the world economic system "[3]. Eli Hexher and Bertil Olin, reflecting the international trade flow and its composition, concluded that the specialization of a particular country depends on the level of ownership of their production factors, and they put forward the theory of "equating prices with production factors."].

Yagdish N. Bhogwati proved that increasing export orientation under certain conditions would lead to a significant deterioration of trade conditions, resulting in a decline in real income [5].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan a number of economists, including A. Alimov, I. Khamedov [6], J. Jalolov, I. Akhmedov, I. Nematov, T. Akramov [7], G.G. Nazarova, NN Mahmudov [8].

Research Methodology

The article studies the stages of globalization in the development of international trade and international trade based on observations, the economic analysis of the dynamics of changes in the export and import of fruits and vegetables by the selective method of the republic.

Analysis and results

Recommendations and recommendations on the effective use of marketing methods for the establishment of a permanent platform for the fruit and vegetable fairs fair and the conclusion of export contracts for the next year are developed.

The enterprises analyze the natural losses in storage, transportation and sale of wet fruits and vegetables and grapes, and develop recommendations for regulating the activities of non-oil exporters. At the same time, the exporters are provided with methods of analyzing the presence of overdue accounts receivable on foreign trade contracts and the part of the export proceeds in foreign currency on the basis of non-timely sale to authorized banks.

Strengthening measures of legal impact on insurers, up to 0.1% of the minimum authorized capital for insurers in accordance with the insurance activity legislation, for breach of terms of payment of insurance contracts under export contracts, as well as accounting and reporting requirements for insurance of export contracts Application of fines in the prescribed manner will be described in detail.

As a result of the special attention given to improving the production system in farms, recommendations are given to implement measures to develop the product storage and processing system and to increase export potential through the introduction of new types of equipment and technology in production.

At the same time in the system of production and export of agricultural products the following issues will be covered in detail:

- Providing farms with quality seeds, disease-resistant and high-yielding varieties;
- Increasing the level of mechanization of production based on the establishment of a system of techniques and mechanisms necessary for the effective implementation of agro-technical activities;
- minimizing losses in product selection, packaging and transportation through infrastructure development, especially in fruit and vegetable production;
- Increasing the profitability of farm production through the development of marketing and information and consulting services for marketing products.

Providing reliable protection of small business and private entrepreneurship and farms in the country, reforming the agrarian sector, implementing significant work to establish rural industries and processing enterprises proposals and recommendations on the development of the industry will be developed.

In general, following the objectives of the study, the following key issues were highlighted:

- to identify and theoretically illuminate the factors of foreign trade influencing sustainable economic growth;
- improvement of the methodology for determining the competitiveness of fruit and vegetable products based on the peculiarities of the global market;

- studying international experience of state support of export of fruit and vegetable products and their introduction in the conditions of Uzbekistan;
- Analysis of the current state of exports and peculiarities of fruit and vegetable production;
- development of economic mechanisms to increase the competitiveness of fruit and vegetable products on the world market;
- Identification of ways to create high value in the industry, create new jobs and increase the incomes of the rural population;
- Improvement of legal, economic and organizational mechanisms for the implementation and implementation of priority directions for export of fruit and vegetable products.

The results of research show that in the long term, direct or processed exports of fruits and vegetables and melons for domestic consumption will provide greater opportunities for Uzbekistan in the world markets. Despite the fact that the country has been developing every year the export of fruits, vegetables, melons and gourds, despite the great potential, these activities are not yet organized.

Most of the vegetables, fruits and grapes grown in the country are consumed by the population. In particular, in 2018, 80.0% of the total vegetables produced, 75.5% of the fruit and 67.9% of the grapes were consumed by the population for domestic consumption.

The rest of the produce is distributed to seed, processing and export. In particular, 15.8% of vegetables, 20.8% of fruits and 24.8% of grapes were processed in 2018. The share of exports in the total amount of wet fruits and vegetables remains low. For example, in 2017, 2.6% of vegetables produced, 7.7% of fruits and 6.9% of grapes were exported, while in 2018 these figures were 2.4%, fruits 3.7% and grapes 7.3%. . As you can see, in 2017, the share of exports in the structure of gross output decreased by 0.2% in vegetables, 4.0% in fruits and 0.4% in grapes. This is due to the fact that in our country a great deal of attention is paid to the export of finished products with high added value on the basis of deep processing of raw materials. Of the fruits and vegetables and melons exported from Uzbekistan to the world markets, vegetables and fruits are the most important.

The advantages of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the export of fruit and vegetable products are as follows:

- High experience and potential of Uzbekistan in cultivation of vegetables, fruits and grapes;

- Presence of rich, diverse varieties, unique quality of fruits, vegetables, melons and grapes that do not resemble in world selection;
- Unique soil-climatic conditions of Uzbekistan, average number of sunny days in the country 320 days a year, consistent exchange of all four seasons creates favorable conditions for cultivation of the main varieties of high-quality fruits and vegetables;
- provide access to markets, vegetables, grapes, melons, dates, and quince throughout the year as a result of the continuing agricultural season from early March to early December;
- Inexpensive consumption properties of fruits and vegetables grown in our country, such as natural sugars, amino and organic acids, essential micronutrients for health, and medicinal properties as a result of the irreplaceable biological substances in the diet;
- Uzbekistan has long been famous for its apricots, peaches, plums, pears, cherries, figs, pomegranates, quince, grapes, tomatoes, cucumbers, onions, garlic and many other fruits and vegetables, a unique taste and aroma. .

Successful functioning of Uzbekistan's economy in the conditions of a market economy depends on their well-balanced, well-organized and economically sound operation. The criteria for their operation are not only their ability to function, but also the necessary conditions for sustainable development, as today there is a severe competition for the choice of consumers in the global goods and services.

Achieving these goals poses new challenges in selecting a development model that meets the interests and capabilities of the entire national economy of Uzbekistan. Searching for industry development models requires identifying priority partners by criteria such as natural and climatic factors, socio-demographic, material and financial, and other factors, such as geographical location, market and product development.

The current system of stimulating the development of the fruit and vegetable production system is characterized by its inability to adapt to the changing market economy. The analysis of the current financial, credit, investment and tax policy of the state shows that there is still no stable mechanism of functioning of the sector, which does not provide the necessary conditions for the development of this sector and the whole agro-industrial complex in the country.

Leaving the industry out of the current situation requires the development of new incentive systems, overcoming the ongoing crisis and ensuring sustainable development.

According to local and international experts, the volume of sales of fruit and vegetables in the country will continue to grow slowly. Therefore, increasing exports can play a crucial role in network development.

The solution of these problems requires comprehensive account of growing competition not only in the Russian market, but also in the markets of other countries.

The experience of developed countries in the fruit and vegetable production sector (Hungary, Russia, Kazakhstan, etc.) shows that in a few years large joint ventures and other successful companies have squeezed small processing enterprises. The basis of their success was the payment terms for raw materials. They also received a down payment. As a result, only small businesses that have their own source of raw materials or control their source of raw materials can continue their operations.

Secondly, by encouraging the export of fruit and vegetable and canned products through export subsidies, the government undertakes to pay for each unit exported abroad.

Third, to help local businesses adapt their products to domestic and foreign markets.

For example, this can be achieved by expanding product sales in domestic markets and strengthening market positions in the sector, even if real incomes do not increase. Assistance in product range adaptation will allow gaining regional markets in the CIS.

The current capabilities of the industry allow us to conclude that not only the range and quality of products fully meet the needs of customers in the CIS markets, but also canned fruit and vegetable products by many parameters are superior to those of major market players.

An analysis of the quality of apricot compote, tomato paste and tomato juice performed by us (Table 1).

As a result of comparing the quality of imported products to the markets of the Republic, it was found that the local industry's products surpass imported products in terms of color (brightness and transparency) and fragrance stability. For foreign consumers, the concept of 'naturalness' is linked to 'ecological cleanliness', which is another important reason why exports need to be increased.

Table 1

Comparative analysis of the quality of fruits and vegetables produced and processed locally

Quality Factors	Level of competitiveness		
	Tomato paste	Apricot compote	Tomato juice
Taste	Tomatoes are not boiled, but not saturated	Concentrated with natural apricots	Satisfied
Color	Natural	Bright, translucent	Natural
Dry matter content	Not less than 36%	-	Not less than 40%
The aroma	-	It is typical of apricot scent	Tomato is unique
Stability	Stable	Stable quality throughout the shelf life	Sustainable quality

Source: author development

The range of fruit and vegetable products, according to current normative-technical documents, contains more than one thousand items. Despite the limited range of manufactured products, the assortment takes into account the needs and tastes of consumers and demonstrates the expansion of the range through the use of different and different types of raw materials with the desired quality.

Fruit and vegetable manufacturers lose competitors in terms of their external components of competitiveness. For example, they offer tomato paste with iron caps that are not so comfortable in traditional glass jars in the range of products they export. This shows that the conservative approach to packaging of finished products is still retained in the industry.

In addition to the official quality standards, there are also standards for export of products, which are of good quality intended for sale in foreign markets. Fruit and vegetable products are sold at the enterprise level and, in some cases, by sellers. A number of intermediaries also specialize in the supply of export products. They usually ship 1-5 wagons or several trucks a season. Where the product is delivered will be chosen by agreement between them. In many industries, exports are largely attributable to the volume of canned fruit and vegetable production, which means that almost all of the produce is exported.

All of these negative factors impact our manufacturers operating in foreign markets as partners: insecurity, insecurity, and inability to function broadly, consistently and responsibly.

In the total volume of production of vegetables, fruits and berries, which are the main types of raw materials for fruit and vegetable processing enterprises, the share of small enterprises representing private households is about 60%. They are no longer satisfied with the scale of trade: if previously the family sold the surplus to the market, today households are the main suppliers of fruits and vegetables in the market. As a result, wholesale markets have emerged in all districts - large and medium-sized.

In our opinion, it can serve as a convenient place for the processing enterprises in the wholesale sector, especially in the regions where small agricultural producers pay special attention to increasing the volume of agricultural production.

The products offered today are becoming more and more consumer-oriented, with the markets becoming more segmented. Sales in the Russian market are made mainly by European standards, with the upper segment making up almost 50%. In addition, each individual market has its own requirements for quality and price. Fruit juices of our companies, which are in high demand in the Russian markets, are supplied to a relatively low market segment. At the same time, there is a decrease in supply.

Increase in juice production in the CIS countries, especially in Russia, has become a characteristic feature of the fruit juices market in Russia. The top segment is occupied by juices from Brazil and the Netherlands. In addition, local juice producers have joined the association, which will spur competition.

The increase in exports of fruit and vegetables is also due to the high costs of transportation, customs clearance and poor operation of transport facilities. These adverse factors lead to the fact that deliveries to Russia sometimes take up to three weeks. As a result of increased transportation costs, the fixed price will not be competitive, particularly in the Central and North-Western economic regions of Russia.

The sale of fruit and vegetable products in foreign markets is also associated with an increase in transaction costs. The level of transaction costs is unpredictable and depends on the market conditions and the nature of the partners. This reduces the chances of success of this product by adapting production to market systems.

In order to increase the export of fruits and vegetables, it is necessary to focus on inter-district distribution of fruit and vegetable production, ie production of the same type of products in demand in the domestic and foreign markets in 3-4 districts of each region.

This will allow to increase the volume of export of fruits and vegetables, to export high-quality, high-quality fruit, vegetables, fruits and vegetables, in accordance with the requirements of foreign buyers.

Conclusion/Recommendations

In the long term, direct or processed exports of excess fruit and vegetables for domestic consumption will provide Uzbekistan with great opportunities in the world markets. Despite the fact that the country has been developing every year the export of fruit and vegetable products, despite the huge potential, these activities have not been done yet. Most of the vegetables, fruits and grapes grown in our country are consumed by the population. In particular, in 2018, 80.0% of the total vegetables produced, 75.5% of the fruit and 67.9% of the grapes were directed to the domestic consumption by the population.

Uzbekistan has extensive experience and potential in growing vegetables, fruits and grapes, and there is a rich variety of fruits and vegetables, melons and grapes that are not unique in the world selection. The unique soil and climatic conditions of Uzbekistan, the average number of sunny days in our country on average 320 days a year, and the consistent exchange of all four seasons create favorable conditions for the cultivation of the main varieties of high quality fruits and vegetables. Favorable climatic conditions allow the country to supply fruit, vegetables, grapes, melons, dates and quince all year round. The invaluable properties of the fruits and vegetables produced are medicinal properties as a result of their high content of natural sugars, amino and organic acids, the most important micronutrients and irreplaceable biological substances in the diet. Uzbekistan has long been known for its apricots, peaches, plums, pears, cherries, figs, pomegranates, quince, grapes, tomatoes, cucumbers, onions, garlic, onions and many other fruits and vegetables.

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